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GENRE MATTERS: ENHANCING READING COMPREHENSION AMONG COLOMBIAN UNIVERSITY STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

The current study aimed at demonstrating how the Genre-Based Approach (GBA, from this moment on) enhances Colombian tertiary students' reading comprehension skills. Regarding the background, it took place at a private Higher Education Institution in Colombia; whose focus group was six last semester-students who were around twenty and thirty years old, chosen based on pre-test results, using two from the highest, two from the medium, and the two from the lowest scores; by using expository (cause-effect) texts. To this effect, in regard to the study methodology, only the deconstruction stage of the teaching-learning cycle was developed to expose learners to the structure, language features, common words, expressions, and organization of this type of text, which was led by the teacher in an entire modeling stage. Thus, its data was gathered using three different quantitative and qualitative techniques, also two pre-tests and two post-tests were implemented, and some surveys in forms of questionnaires were applied to the focus group in order to triangulate the results objectively. About the results, it revealed a positive incidence of GBA on the subjects' reading comprehension levels (literal, inferential, and critical thinking), enhancing their skills individually and contributing to some other findings. To conclude, it is essential to acknowledge previously the population weaknesses and strengths, since Genre-Based Approach was applied taking into account their needs, interests and context.

KEYWORDS: English as a Foreign Language (EFL), Genre-Based Approach (GBA), Teaching-Learning Cycle, Reading Comprehension Skills, Reading Strategies.

1. INTRODUCTION

In Colombia, many students coming at their professional careers face difficulties when addressing content-based texts. More than not having the knowledge in the academic field, they lack the necessary strategies to understand content ideas. The academic tasks, learners, were exposed to within the project; involve reading and learning new and heavy content, which is even harder to perform in a foreign language. Therefore, instruction for reading comprehension tasks plays a major role. Learners, who are taught how to deal with reading strategies and how to use them, have more chances to improve their reading comprehension levels and, clearly, their results in standardized tests. This study sought to implement the Genre-Based Approach (GBA) and the strategies within its cycle so learners could understand expository texts in content-area materials and, therefore, to be able to answer questions dealing with the literal, inferential, and critical thinking levels of reading comprehension.

Some studies have been conducted on the importance of developing reading comprehension skills. According to Hagaman & Reid (2008), although reading plays a key component in academic success, and learners have a wide number of strategies to improve their reading comprehension at their disposal, research focused on those reading comprehension strategies is very little. Moreover, little is known about if the GBA can really improve learners' reading comprehension skills when dealing with expository texts as most research has focused on narrative ones. This is the reason why the current study aimed to demonstrate its effectiveness.

Other studies have worked on strategies to improve learners' reading comprehension skills in the academic field, but we still know little about how the GBA can contribute to improving learners' performance when taking tests that ask them to answer literal, inferential, and critical thinking questions, which are present in international tests. Learning around text genres has gained importance in the EFL/ESL teaching contexts. Martin in Chappell (2004 p. 9) states that the number of stages within the cycles of the GBA have special objectives, which translates into a wide number of activities where learners have the opportunity to immerse in the context of culture and social purpose of the text, and the role of the language within the task.

Consequently, the importance of this research relies on the fact that Colombia has obtained low scores in international tests. According to the recent results of the Program for International Student Assessment (PISA), which assesses 15-year-old

students, 47% Colombian high school graduates are below the minimum level of the test or Level 2. Moreover, the Progress in International Reading Literacy (PIRLS), a test that is held in 48 countries, also concluded that the performance in reading comprehension in Colombian secondary education is very low. In the most recent PIRLS measurement, Colombian high schoolers obtained a score of 448 (low level) over 675 (advanced level). The Third Regional Comparative and Explanatory Study (TERCE), which is used by 15 different countries, showed Colombia held the seventh place in the reading comprehension skill.

Although prestigious Colombian universities have conducted studies to analyze this scenery. Universidad de la Sabana supported PISA results through a study of the Reading and Writing Network in Higher Education (Red de Lectura y Escritura en Educación Superior). Mario Lozano, professor of the Department of Languages at this institution and one of the main researchers of the study, states that first semester students "read, understand and infer, but when they get to the process of critical reading, the situation gets complicated.". On the other hand, the situation looks a little worse in the coastal region, where a reading and writing diagnostic test was applied to second semester students from Universidad del Norte in 2016; which revealed that the 44% had difficulties even to understand the explicit content of a text, to recognize its purpose, and to show a general understanding. The Director of the Spanish Department at this institution, Professor Nayibe Rosado, pointed out in the analysis of these results that a 50% of those students reaches good levels of reading comprehension, but only a 6% of them understood and contextualized the text, at the time they adopted a critical view towards it. Notwithstanding, little is still known about how GBA instruction enhances Colombian students' reading comprehension skills. In addition, how learners' perceptions towards the GBA instruction can play an essential role within the process.

Through the implementation of this research study, we sought to provide learners with a variety of strategies to help them to comprehend the demanding or required content - area texts they were exposed to, especially in international tests. The results of this study provided information on how the GBA and its teaching-learning cycle can ease the reading process and, thus, engage learners with a deeper and more autonomous way of approaching reading passages. Therefore, this case study addressed the following question: To what extent does the Genre-Based Approach (GBA) improve

tenth graders' reading comprehension skills in an L2? In order to fulfil the subsequent research objectives:

To demonstrate how the Genre-Based Approach (GBA) enhances tertiary students' reading comprehension skills.

To determine the subjects' level of proficiency in reading comprehension skills.

To analyze how the GBA instruction influenced the subjects' reading comprehension level.

To analyze learners' perceptions towards the use of the GBA instruction

2. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

This section aims to describe the essential concepts regarding the GBA focused on reading comprehension skills. The current chapter defines the following key concepts essential for the holistic understanding of the research: reading in a foreign language, reading comprehension, reading comprehension strategies, the GBA concept and its teaching-learning cycle.

2.1. Reading in a foreign language

Reading, in any language, is conceived as one of the most essential abilities to develop other related language skills while learning it, especially if the learner is learning a foreign one. Reading in an L2 is defined by Alderson (1984: page 245) as "Once again it has been found that reading English as a foreign language is both a reading problem and a language problem." He pointed this out as there should be what he calls a 'language competence ceiling' before the existing abilities in the first language can begin to be transferred to the second one. This conclusion came after the analysis of 4 hypotheses on why L2 reading is poor, which can be summarized as it follows: firstly, learners lack reading competence in their first language; and secondly, having a meager knowledge of the foreign language under study does not allow learners to transfer the correct strategies from L1 when reading in L2. (Wahyu, D. 2015).

Other researchers, such as Bossers (1991) supported Alderson's claim and provided their own overview of L2 reading. He pointed out that, although L1 reading is significantly important in L2 reading, it only happens at very relatively high levels of the last one: "L1 reading comes into play as a significant predictor variable at a relatively high level of L2 reading." (p. 59).

2.2. Reading Comprehension Strategies

Mastering all components involved in reading turns it into a challenge for readers. To be able to understand a text, a proficient adult reader goes

through processes of decoding, interpreting and constructing. First, he must have a clear comprehension of the elements of a sentence. Then, he has to differentiate new versus given information, which will allow him to reinforce the background information he has about the topic of the text. At more global levels, the reader implicitly identifies the genre, purpose, structure, the author's intention. These apparently happen effortlessly but they are the product of a lot of exposure to reading strategies, which, many times, the reader is not conscious of their use (McNamara, 2007).

A reading comprehension strategy is defined by McNamara (2007) as "a cognitive or behavioural action which is enacted under particular contextual conditions, with the goal of improving some aspect of comprehension." By contextual conditions, she meant the situations that learners encounter when reading. She pointed out the example of finding an unknown word and states the difference between a reader who chooses a behavioural action versus one who uses a cognitive one: the first looks up the word in the dictionary and finds its definition while the second reads the definition, re-reads the sentence having the new definition in mind, and then understands the sentence as a whole.

Other authors such as Edge (2002), in Ulker (2017), define reading comprehension strategies as "strategies that encourage your students to use prior knowledge, experiences, careful thought, and evaluation to help them decide how to practically apply what they know to all reading situations"(p. 4). For Medina (2007) it is not just about learners joining their background knowledge of the text with their experiences because, although comprehension strategies are universal and are at the disposal of those who want to use them, they represent "a complex process" mainly because "some strategies work for some students, and other strategies work for other students, just as some strategies work best with certain types of reading material, other strategies work best with other types of reading material" (Medina, 2007: 6). This is the reason why the teacher's role is crucial in improving learners' reading comprehension as he is the one who can determine the approach to take and the type of text learners will deal with (Ulker, 2017).

2.3. The Genre-Based Approach

This approach looks for a learners' wider understanding throughout the processes of modelling, scaffolding, doing and feedback in order to move forward in the understanding of the comprehensive levels of reading by using different

strategies that help learners to become better readers. Talking about the English language teaching specifically, the GBA has not been widely used; but some theorists are already talking about its stages and also about how it works as it was published in the Journal English Language Teaching (ELT) 2015: "The steps of GBA are BKOF (Building Knowledge of the Field), MOT (Modelling of the Text), JCOT (Joint Construction of the Text), and ICOT (Independent Construction of the Text)" where is stated that Genre-Based Approach uses many strategies to enhance learners state of comprehension taking a certain, specific field as the base to learn.

In the field of English teaching as a foreign language the Genre-Based approach has not been commonly used. Some of the reading tasks involved recognizing, predicting, and recalling patterns; Rodríguez (2017), a foreign Language professor in Colombia, also mentions that the most advisable strategy to teach reading using the GBA is "learning to read: Reading to learn", which means that BGA has a detailed process to follow which is full of stages and tasks per stage, but that process must be guided, measured and assessed by the teacher since it is mainly goal-oriented.

On the other side, Rodríguez (2017: 10) defines GBA in the following terms:

"The use of real material based on specific knowledge purposes rather than the language teaching... Instructing students to read by using different genre texts, which were written for other purposes not for teaching reading within an English as a second/foreign language (ESL/EFL) context."

In other words, this approach encompasses reading comprehension skills development by exposing learners to a specific genre, which will allow them to handle further reading passages belonging to the same type of text.

The approach under study in this paper is chosen as a manner to improve learners' reading comprehension skills by using the strategies and stages mentioned above but which will be detailed explained later in the methodology chapter. Due to learners' results when exposed to content expository texts are not good enough, and because of their position as tenth graders, the Genre-Based Approach teaches learners to focus on main idea, author's perspective, linking words, as well as on using a critical point of view when facing expository texts of higher complexity.

2.4. The Teaching- Learning Cycle

Teaching learners the structure of different types of texts and the language features in each is the basis

of the Genre-Based Approach instruction (Hyon, 1996). Exposure to genres in reading, especially in high-school, is little, which is why the teacher's role in delivering good instructions becomes the key in the success of the implementation of this approach. It is expected that after the instructions learners can be able to identify the aforementioned patterns by themselves, which will allow them to understand the text in an easier and better way.

The core of this approach lies in it cycle because it provides the teacher with a path to follow along the course to be taught. During the stages of the genre orientation, the teacher guides learners through a deconstruction, a joint construction, and an independent construction stage, allowing teachers, as Martin (2009) in Alvarino & Fontalvo (2017) stated "scaffold the process until a knowledge extending". Moreover, learners have the opportunity to see how the language of a specific genre allows them to recognize the text's main idea, purpose, and the author's intention. The cycle previously mentioned is presented in the following figure; however, in order to meet the objectives of this study, the deconstruction phase was the only one carried out. During the deconstruction stage, the teacher models the text in detail and drives learners' attention to the text organization and the language features in it, in order to prepare them to do the same when facing reading comprehension tasks.

For Rose (2015), in Alvarino & Fontalvo (2017: 7), the deconstruction is the stage where reading and discussion take place, which helps learners "go beyond their independent reading level". The teacher's role in this phase of the cycle is to "guide

Figure 1. The teaching-learning cycle (Rothery and Stenglin, 1994, in Martin, 1999).

students to identify and mark key information in each paragraph, building their (students) skills in recognizing and comprehending key information."

Being the deconstruction stage the only one taken from the approach, a series of stages within it,

proposed by Moss, Benítez & Mizuno (2016) in Alvarino and Fontalvo (2017), were taken into consideration by the teacher to design and to carry out lesson plans: contextualization of the genre, teaching the structure of the text, detailed reading, representation of the text ideas, and reaction to the text.

The Genre Pedagogy has served not only ESL/ EFL school contexts but the teaching of ESP courses. Bonyadi (2012) conducted a study to explore the structures, strategies and social functions of 20 newspaper editorials of criticism from The New York Times in function of their communicative purposes. The target group consisted of students majoring in journalism. Within the methodology, Bonyadi states that identifying the schematic parts in the editorials of criticism is not usually as straightforward as people might assume. The results of this research revealed some drawbacks of using the newspaper and its sub-genres as input in ESL/ EFL classrooms if their communicative purpose, schematic structures and syntactic patterns are not dealt with at the first stage. Therefore, a variety of pedagogical implications for EFL/ESP educators was suggested. To start, learners should be sensitive to genre distinctions; otherwise, the core features of newspaper language would be lost, making it weak. If there is a chance of falling into the previous situation, Bonyadi suggests L2 teachers to design interesting class tasks based on editorials, seeking to transform learners into critical readers, capable of reading between lines. The idea is not to make genre analysis counterproductive. Finally, Restrepo (2022) states that using active methodologies in language classes is a highly effective approach to develop critical thinking since in addition to its advantages it focuses on meaningful learning.

Alvarino & Fontalvo (2017) also implemented the GBA to develop reading competencies, especially when exposing learners to the social and functional purposes of English language. This action research study took 40 high school students at a public school in Soledad, Atlántico, Colombia, who were exposed to different text types and their structures in order to foster reading and facilitate language learning. Data was collected before, during and after the implementation of the GBA strategies, going from instruments such as questionnaires, interviews and document analysis before the implementation to class observations, to video recordings and lesson plans analysis during it, and checklists afterwards, in order to evaluate the results and impact of the proposal. The results showed significant effects of the GBA pedagogy on developing reading competences

as, along the process, the teacher constantly supported learners throughout the genre stages at the time they learnt to work collaboratively and actively engage in the reading process. To sum up, the above-mentioned studies suggest that the arguments to implement the Genre-Based Approach are solid and could prove usefulness for second language education.

3. METHODOLOGY

The current research mixes qualitative with quantitative methods, which provide a more reliable and fruitful source of data collection for obtaining wider and more concrete results that specifically answer the research question under study. Qualitative research is described as a flexible procedure in which the researcher's perspective counts and many external factors can influence the results. Hence, according to Creswell (2014: 104):

Qualitative research is an approach for exploring and understanding the meaning for individuals or groups ascribe to a social or human problem. The process of research involves emerging questions and procedures. Data typically collected in the participants' setting, data analysis inductively building from particulars to general themes, and the researcher making interpretations of the meaning of the data. The final written report has a flexible structure and those who engage in this form of inquiry support a way of looking at research that honors an inductive style.

3.1. Creswell also defines quantitative research in the following terms:

The approach of testing objective theories by examining the relationship among variables. These variables, in turn, can be measured, typically on instruments, so that numbered data can be analyzed using statistical procedures. The final written report has a set structure consisting of introduction, literature and theory, methods, results, and discussions, those researchers who engage in this form of inquiry have assumptions about testing theories deductively. (Op. Cit., page number).

In other words, Creswell points out the objectivity of quantitative research which are based on measurable facts more than in beliefs or inferences from subjects' attitudes or perspectives.

A recurrent practice nowadays is the mixed methods in which both approaches are used; it has been proved that both acting together provide a deeper understanding of the phenomenon rather than the approach itself. Creswell (2014: 78) explains this innovative resource as:

The approach to inquiry involving collecting both quantitative and qualitative data, integrating the two forms of data, and using distinct designs that may involve philosophical assumptions and theoretical frameworks... The combination of both approaches provides a more complete understanding of a research problem than either approach alone.

This study implemented various data collection methods; among them there are from qualitative and quantitative ones, that is the reason why the current research use mixed method; As the research objective is to seek for describing and measuring the degree of improvement on learners' reading comprehension level, is drastically necessary to implement the former and the latter data collection methods which provide a broad description (qualitative) and concise results (quantitative) of the problem.

3.2. Research Design

For this research, the method implemented was a Case Study, specifically the descriptive case study, which is defined by Duff (1990) (p. 119) as "... case study may involve more than one subject... it may be based on particular groups (e.g. group's dynamics within a classroom); organizations or events..." This quotation explains how the case study works, arguing that it can be carried out taking into account various subjects or target groups. Implementing a case study relies on the researcher's considerations regarding the context conditions and if they are highly relevant to the issue under investigation (McKay, 2006).

Yin (2003) (p. 286) supports that the case study design seeks to:

1. Explain and describe the causes of real-life events within a particular group.
2. Describe the intervention and the surroundings where it occurred. The intention is to analyze the different dimensions the research altered. The previous description corresponds to the action research case study.
3. Evaluate a particular case, such as the impact of the implementation on a new curriculum at a school.

Designing and carrying out a case study requires the researcher to follow a series of features. Yin (2003) states that every case study must have:

1. A research question, which is in the form of a "how" or "why".
2. A proposition, typically pointing at the direction of where to look for significant data.
3. A unit of analysis or the definition of the

boundaries of the case. After defining it, the researcher will be able to study similar cases.

4. Cohesion between the data and the proposition, which is achievable by looking for patterns in the data that support the study's proposition.
5. Criteria for interpreting the findings. The researcher will find the evidence that supports a particular proposition with the evidence.

This research was set out as a case study due to the type of population and the setting where it takes place; the subjects under study were observed and also intervened, and the results before, during, and after intervention were part of the analysis of the data. A case study as such is merely descriptive; it means that any detail, result, event or phenomena found that results important for the current research must be described in-depth, which makes this study different from other case studies is that, although researchers will teach learners how to use different strategies that let them handle any expository text; the results depend on to what extent learners learn how to use and to apply them.

3.3. Context and participants

This research took place in a higher Education Institution (HEI) in Colombia, which offers around 16 different undergraduate programs at the professional levels. It focused on the particular event of a last semester student of six different careers from the same faculty, currently enrolled in an Upper-Intermediate English course. The participants, whose ages are around 20 and 30 years, belonged to middle and high socioeconomic status. This sample was taken considering their drawbacks in inferential and critical thinking skills when dealing with content-written passages.

Given the exploratory nature of this research and its focus on understanding how the Genre-Based Approach operates within a specific instructional context, the study adopted a small, purposive sample of higher education EFL students. This sample size is consistent with mixed-methods case study designs, which prioritize in-depth analysis of pedagogical processes and classroom interactions rather than statistical representativeness. The limited number of participants allowed for detailed observation of the deconstruction phase of the Genre-Based Approach and facilitated the integration of qualitative and quantitative data to capture changes in students' literal, inferential, and critical reading comprehension.

However, the sample size and the focus on a single institutional context in Colombia limit the

generalizability of the findings. The results should therefore be interpreted as context-specific insights rather than broadly generalizable conclusions about EFL instruction. Factors such as institutional characteristics, students' language proficiency levels, and instructional practices may influence the outcomes in other settings. Future research with larger and more diverse samples across multiple institutions would help determine the extent to which the observed benefits of the Genre-Based Approach can be replicated in different educational contexts.

4. DATA COLLECTION TECHNIQUES

Studies that rely on mixed-methods practices imply the use of both quantitative and qualitative data collection techniques either in sequential, concurrent or iterative patterns. (Caracelli & Greene, 1997 in Sandelowski 2000).

The combined use of the aforementioned methods can be used to fulfil a variety of objectives. The data gathered by the use of those techniques allowed the researcher to turn quantitative data into qualitative and qualitative into quantitative one; For instance, the quantitative results from this study's pre-test were analyzed in order to describe participants' current competence of reading comprehension. This instrument also achieved the purpose of choosing the participants of the study and the kind of information that was obtained from them.

Besides the pre-tests, a genre-based course will be designed where the main features of the approach will be reflected on a set of lesson plans, which aim to bind the objectives of the course. Surveys were carried out in the current study in order to know learners' perceptions towards the use of Genre-Based Approach, which will enable the researchers to gather objective data "at some degree", and complement these data with the previously mentioned tests from the participants under study.

Questionnaires are defined by Brown (2001: 6) as "any written instrument that presents respondents with a series of questions or statements to which they are to react either by writing out their answers or selecting them among existing manners."

Surveys in the form of questionnaires provide with data on attitudes and opinions from a large group of participants allowing researchers to find out information that participants can report about themselves. The type of survey that will be applied will be a structure close one which provides with a set of possible answers since they do not allow respondents to answer in the way they see fit, as it is explained by Mackey & Gass (2005) "close-item

questionnaires typically involve a greater uniformity of measurement and therefore greater reliability."

This leads to an easier way of quantifying and analyzing the data and henceforth in a less unexpected and subjective information. Reading proficiency tests (open-ended) were applied in quantitative research to measure participants' performance in the skill assessed.

4.1. Data Analysis

This chapter aims to use all data gathered in order to analyze it, leading the objectives and the research questions' methodology. The results and analysis of this study lie on the triangulation of its three data collection techniques. In its early stage, a pre-test was applied, which allowed researchers to gather information regarding learners' strengths and areas to improve when answering literal, inferential and critical thinking questions.

In the same way, the outcomes of the implementation were examined by analyzing a set of five lesson plans and their corresponding activities, along with learners' perception of the implementation of the approach, which was gathered through an interview applied to learners. The contrast between the transcription of the interviews and the activities planned on the lessons allowed us to check the effectiveness of the GBA implementation and the impact of the proposal.

4.2. Lesson Plans Analysis

During the implementation of this proposal to foster reading comprehension skills, the teacher guided learners through a series of activities directed to analyze cause-effect genre. The lessons were designed to enhance learners' understanding of the language immersed in cause-effect texts and, this way, ease their reading comprehension, not only to be able to answer questions but to understand the main idea of the text, its purpose, and be able to summarize it, orally or written. Through the stages of the lesson plans, learners were supported by the teacher, at some points more than at others.

Lesson 1: Contextualization of the Topic

The first moment that the lessons covered was the contextualization of the topic. Here, the teacher introduced the topic (addictions) through a discussion of what learners thought an addiction was and what caused one. Then, learners used strategies such as note taking, predicting and inferring to get the main idea of the text and, consequently, be able to answer comprehension questions. The aim of this first part was to activate prior knowledge about

additions so learners could link it in the upcoming stages. Activities in this lesson helped the teacher get a broader idea of how learners performed when understanding aural texts.

Lesson 2: Genre Input

The teacher proceeded to provide learners with the input of the genre under study. To do it, a video was presented to show what the cause-effect texts intention is, and the most common words and expressions used in the genre under study. Then, several exercises were modelled by the teacher for learners to identify those words and expressions within paragraphs.

Up to this point, the class was mostly teacher-centered. It was necessary not to leave any features (purpose, common words and expressions) of the genre unclear. Although this stage involved learners in the later parts, one of the subjects under study suggested they should be active the whole time.

Moves	Actor	Discourse
11	T	Basados en el nivel de inglés que cada uno tiene y en su estilo de aprendizaje específico, ¿qué llamó más tu atención de las clases? ¿Qué cambiarías? ¿Materiales? ¿Grupos o tiempo de trabajo?
12	L1	A mí me gustó la temática y los textos que ustedes... me parecieron interesantes y pues yo creo que si se toma al estudiante y se pone a él a hacer él mismo a hacer la misma cosa; no sé cómo explicarlo, o sea si el estudiante es el que encuentra o sea el que vivencia lo que se está aprendiendo me parece que es más... o sea es mejor para él por ejemplo a mí me gusta más aprender así como por mí misma, haciendo. No que la profesora esté ahí en clase ahí magistral, no, sino que yo tenga también como una participación.

Lesson 3: Deconstruction

The third lesson was the deconstruction, where the teacher modelled first, and the amount of opportunities for students to participate was higher. Having in mind these students like to participate, the deconstruction, which is supposed to be done all by the teacher, was shared. During it, learners could not only engage in activities to improve their comprehension of the text but they could discuss their thoughts and perceptions.

Before moving to the deconstruction stage, learners were asked to organize a jumbled text about caffeine. They were arranged in smaller groups to perform this task. The teacher proposed them to highlight the key words or expressions that indicated the position of each paragraph.

As learners carried out the activity, it was possible for the teacher to notice how easy or difficult was for them to find context clues that helped them identify the sequence of the text. During the monitoring, she approached some groups and did some mediation for them to realize what the right order was. During this stage, interaction among learners was promoted. Collaborative activities were highly significant to them because they see group work as a strategy through which they can clarify doubts at the time they improve communication. Learners enjoy contrasting their answers with their peers.

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Moves	Actor	Discourse
3	T	¿Qué piensan ustedes de las actividades llevadas a cabo?
4	L2	Bueno lo que pienso es que fueron muy didácticas porque a muchos de nosotros simplemente nos aburre cuando vamos a leer y esas cosas, pero las profesoras, las maestras la convirtieron en una actividad didáctica debido a que utilizamos herramientas tecnológicas,

		utilizamos la comunicación, los grupos, y hablamos mucho que fue lo más importante, no sólo estuvimos escuchando a la profesora sino que también nosotros hicimos ahí.
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She focused Ss' attention to the cause-effect one and started to use the information from the text to complete it. After modelling the first two paragraphs, learners continued with the remaining ones by filling in the graphic organizer on a paper sheet.

By having learners extract the information from the text and organize it in the graphic organizer, it was possible to approach the different learning styles among the class. Learners felt this strategy improved the way they summarize texts.

Lesson 4: Graphic Representation

The fourth stage in the development of the lesson plans is representing the text's ideas. During this moment, the teacher showed learners the variety of graphic organizers used for the different text genres.

Moves	Actor	Discourse
9	T	Después de todo el trabajo, ¿podrías citar algunas actividades/ ejercicios que te hayan facilitado la comprensión de los textos leídos?
10	L6	Sí, por cierto lo de causa y efecto que coloquemos por acá la causa y por acá los efectos; como dijo la profesora si nos hubiesen mandado a hacer un resumen del texto que nos hubiesen mandado a leer como el de la cafeína, se me hubiera hecho más difícil sin haber encontrado las causas y efectos porque no teníamos como que la base entonces esa estrategia de esa clase nos ayudó mucho.

Moves	Actor	Discourse
5	T	Ok. Perfecto. La segunda es piensan ustedes, ¿qué piensan ustedes de las actividades que se llevaron a cabo?
7	L4	A mí me pareció que las actividades eran de mucha ayuda y eran dinámicas que le permitían al estudiante decir como comprender independientemente de su modo de estudio ya que había diversidad de, pues de métodos de, de métodos y técnicas de enseñanza. Además, hay, el hecho de que sean tan variadas nos permitió aparte de enfatizar en el tema propio era dar un repaso a lo que ya se había dado pues como había dicho mi compañera Manuela. Por ejemplo, el tema de la organización de cuadros nos estaban repasando el scanning y nos enseñaban a organizar el texto para redactarlo de forma más resumida en un summary.

Lesson 5: Independent deconstruction

During the independent deconstruction, learners read a text about a different topic than the one used in the deconstruction. They used strategies such as skimming and scanning, previously worked in class, to look for unknown vocabulary and those words

and expressions found in cause-effect texts. After sharing their answers as a group, they used the graphic organizer to extract the most important information from the text. Having it, they were able to answer comprehension questions in an easy and faster way.

Moves	Actor	Discourse
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1	T	¿Cuál creen ustedes que fueron los objetivos de las clases?
2	L2	Bueno los principales objetivos de las clases fue que nosotros identificamos principalmente las causas y efectos en textos es decir, cómo fortalecer nuestra comprensión lectora eso lo podemos evidenciar con actividades como: la de reconocer los conectores que hay en ciertos textos, eso lo hicimos en grupo y fue muy interesante porque la comunicación entre todos los estudiantes favoreció a que nosotros entendiéramos más los textos, también que pudiéramos tener una secuencia lógica de cada texto como lo hicimos cuando pegamos los párrafos para formar el texto.

During the implementation of these 5 lessons, the teacher constantly monitored learners' performance, even in the independent deconstruction of the text. This was highly valued by learners who claimed that, although they like to work by themselves, they appreciate the teacher corrected any mistake they had.

		porqué de que, el por qué era una causa y no un efecto entonces uno quedaba satisfecho con la explicación que ella daba.
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Moves	Actor	Discourse
26	T	Excelente. Bueno, la última pregunta es muy clara, ¿la retroalimentación que se les brindó después de cada actividad fue suficiente fue efectiva?
27	Ls3 - 4	Sí.
28	L4	Sí fue efectiva debido a que a través de esta o con su ayuda nosotros podíamos identificar de una forma cuál era nuestro error y poder aprender de él que es lo que nosotros necesitamos si queremos trascender en cuanto a nuestros conocimientos
29	L3	Además nos aclaraba las dudas, por ejemplo, a veces pensábamos que una parte era un efecto pero pues vamos a ver que era una causa entonces ella nos, nos aclaraba el

Moves	Actor	Discourse
9	T	Después de todo el trabajo, ¿podrías citar algunas actividades/ ejercicios que te hayan facilitado la comprensión de los textos leídos?
10	L2	Bueno, la actividad que dije de los párrafos, de organizar los párrafos, de reconocer cuáles son los conectores de causa y efecto, también la socialización porque hay cosas que nosotros obviamos pero nuestros compañeros o nuestros profesores nos dicen, esas actividades sí.

Analysis of the Tests

The current study carried some bifunctional pre-tests out, which allowed the researcher and teacher-researcher to first, select the focus group under study and second, to objectively know which exact level of reading comprehension they were in. Subsequently,

the lesson plans entirely designed by the teachers, were developed following most of Genre-Based Approach's process. The post-tests were held afterward to quantitatively determine to what extent did tenth graders improve their reading comprehension skills with the aim of answer the research question previously mentioned; as it is seen in the following tables.

Table 1: Pre-tests and Post-tests Results by Reading Comprehension by Levels.

SUBJECT	READING COMPREHENSION LEVELS	PRE-TESTS	POST-TEST
L1	Literal	75%	83%
	Inferential	38%	50%
	Critical thinking	71%	67%
L2	Literal	75%	100%
	Inferential	63%	67%
	Critical thinking	100%	83%
L3	Literal	63%	100%
	Inferential	38%	67%
	Critical thinking	71%	100%
L4	Literal	50%	67%
	Inferential	63%	50%
	Critical thinking	71%	67%
L5	Literal	50%	83%
	Inferential	25%	50%
	Critical thinking	29%	50%
L6	Literal	50%	80%
	Inferential	38%	67%
	Critical thinking	57%	67%

By the authors.

Table 2: Subjects' Progress in Reading Comprehension by Levels

READING COMPREHENSION LEVEL	PRE-TEST	POST-TEST	PROGRESS
Literal level	60%	86%	+ 25%
Inferential level	44%	58%	+ 15%
Critical thinking level	67%	72%	+ 6%

By analyzing the results from the pre-tests, it could be identified that learners mainly presented difficulties in the literal and in the inferential levels. In the former, the population did not reach a significant percentage since half of it obtained 50% of the answers right while the rest was under 76%. In the latter, 4 of the subjects obtained results under 39%, being the minimum 25%, while the remaining 2 got 63%. All of the above represented a concern based on the grade and level they were in, and the exposure to the language they have had. Although the most demanding level is the critical thinking. Most of the subjects did not present the same difficulties as in the literal and inferential levels, since they felt more engaged with reading when it was linked to their life experiences.

After the implementation of the genre-based

approach, two post-tests were applied. The results showed an increase in all levels. For the literal, 5 of the subjects were above 79%, where 2 of them got 100%, two of them got 83%, and one of them got 80%. On the other hand, some of the learners with the lowest scores in this level increased 100% or almost it.

Based on the pre-tests' results, it is possible to affirm that in the inferential level is in which learners had more problems with at the beginning; As it is shown in the last table; the four subjects with the lowest percentages belong to this category; and comparing those percentages with the ones obtained in the post-tests is seen a big increase for instance, both with 38% at the initial part got 67% at the end, which means that obtained a 76% of increase, the other with the same percentage in the pre-test later got a 50% who improved in a 31.57%; but the highest improvement is seen in the subject with the lowest score at the beginning in which a 25% became a 50% which represents a significant improvement of the 100% and the last low score improved from 29% in the first to 50% in the last one, enhancing a 72.41%

Before analyzing the results of the critical thinking level, there are several considerations to be taken into account. As stated before, this level represents a major challenge for learners as it demands the process of linking the text with their life experiences. Therefore, if they do not find any relationship between both, the questions will be poorly or not answered at all. Furthermore, the extent in which learners have been exposed to the content under study highly influences the quality of their answers. In this regard, the increase in this level was not as high as the other two, which should be considered meaningful as it takes longer to develop in learners, when comparing it with the latter ones.

In general, there was a higher improvement in the literal level (25%), followed by the inferential (15%) and the critical thinking one (6%). These advances are attributed to the permanent use of the reading strategies within the approach, which focused on teaching learners how to identify the main idea of texts, to look up the specific details that were necessary to answer the questions, and to use the information from the text to answer the inferential questions accurately. Besides, the instruction on deconstructing the texts to identify their structure and, consequently, their main goals, helped learners to easily skim them and to recognize where features, such as the author's opinion was, when they were not literally written.

5. CONCLUSIONS

This main purpose of this research was to measure the potential of the GBA in helping tenth graders to improve their reading comprehension skills. In doing so, a course was designed and implemented by the teacher and the teacher-researcher, four tests, two pre-tests and two post-tests) were carried out, the six subjects (2 high, 2 medium, and two low achievers) were interviewed and recorded as well; to be transcribed later.

The implementation of the current research has drawn a set of conclusions in terms of: Interaction, acknowledgement, proficiency, accuracy, frustration, and motivation. As it was shown when the triangulation process took place, the usage of the Genre- Approach enhanced classroom interaction on all sides; Teacher-students and students--students and it could improve learners' relationship inside and outside the class. Furthermore, was possible to co-construct knowledge cumulatively, as it is evidenced in the lesson plans with group, pair work and with teacher's feedback and proved with learners' testimony in the interviews. Besides, learners could first recognize their main shortfalls as well as their strengths in reading comprehension in order to take action on them. Also, in terms of proficiency since learners became more active readers due to the use of genre-based approach as they learned many formal aspects of the English language. One of the most essential issues to be considered in a language classroom is the reduction of learners' frustration, which was substantially reduced through the deconstruction process, led by the teacher, among low and middle achievers.

Another finding revealed was the importance to

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recognize the appropriate usage of the Genre-Based Approach depending on the context, in other words, for implementing the strategy under study is mandatory to take into account the population's proficiency level, its level of reading comprehension, its preferences in terms of readings, what are they exposed the most to? Since teachers who use the approach under discussion should take into account learners' exposure to the aforementioned issues in order to obtain great improvements in each learner's reading comprehension level in spite of which each one is; as it was evidenced in the current study in which the process had to be adjusted to learners' levels without losing the original process.

Furthermore, as a manner to summarize, we determined that the implementation of a new method or strategy is always a hard and a long process, and GBA is not the exception, there were some issues that jeopardized our record of evidence, and actually, it was not possible to apply all necessary tests.

Despite the positive results we got in the study we also faced some limitations, for instance the insufficient amount of time required to assess learners more throughout the process, since there were many external activities at school due to they were tenth graders, it is recognizably possible to affirm that the Genre-Based Approach in fact, improved tenth graders' reading comprehension skills, based on our evidence, on learners performance after the course, on their scores in the post-tests and on their opinions in the interviews, as well.

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